

PRAGMATIC INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPT OF "APOLOGY" IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES.

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Abstract. An apology is defined by many researchers and linguists as an expression of regret. For example, Leech (1983:125) views an apology as an expression of regret by (S) for an offense committed against (H). He sees the apology as an acknowledgment of the imbalance in the relationship between (S) and (H) and an attempt to restore balance. Accordingly, the idea of defining an apology as an expression of remorse seems somewhat controversial.

Keywords. Apology , conceptosphere, embarrass, imbalance, face-saving.

Many linguists believe that an apology is not always an expression of regret. Thomas (1995:100) argues that the Searlian rules that Searle (1969) has shown to control speech performance cannot be applied to the following example: "I'm sorry, I spoiled water".

Problems with these rules arise because an apology here is not an expression of remorse:

Prepositional act: The speaker expresses his regret for being spilled.

Preparatory act: The speaker believes that spilling the water is not in your best interest.

Sincerity Condition: The speaker is sorry for spilling the water.

Important condition: Saying "I'm sorry for breaking your nose", the speaker apologizes to you.

Thomas criticizes the Searlian rule, which fails to provide an example in which an apology does not imply remorse.[Thomas. Jenny. (1995). Meaning in Interaction: An Introduction to Pragmatics. London: Longman Group.] Another view is suggested by Fasold (1998:154), who thinks that an apology involves regret but that remorse does not.[Fasold . R (1996). The Sociolinguistics of Language. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers] He calls the phrase "I'm sorry" an indirect apology and gives a vivid example of his point:

A-My aunt Suha died last week.

B-I'm sorry.

A-My aunt Suha died last week.

B-I apologize.

Here "I'm sorry" does not reflect an apology when receiving the news that someone has died, as it is to express regret, but not to accept responsibility. The speaker in the second exchange takes responsibility for Suha's death. If the general idea of apologizing is identified, it is acceptable to associate apologizing with regret. In most cases, an apology can be seen as a rite of passage, in which there is no remorse for what you have done. In addition, people sometimes apologize for future actions for which there is no room for regret. For example: "I'm sorry but I have to report you".

Whether the listener's face or the speaker's face is apologizing, as well as how the apology is politely asked (Ogiermann 2009: 49). Brown and Levinson (1987) argue that apologies can be classified as negative politeness strategies, that is, strategies that focus on the listener's right to be "uninhibited by others." When a speaker apologizes, as Olstein and Cohen (1990: 46-47) explain, he is "willing to humiliate himself to some extent and admit his guilt and responsibility for [the transgression]". Therefore, according to Brown and Levinson, an apology saves face for the listener and threatens the speaker. Holmes (1990: 159) offers a similar view, in which an apology is "discourse directed at B's needs in face and intended to remedy the offense for which A has assumed responsibility, thereby restoring the balance between A and B movement".

However, the issue of face related to apologies can be considered not only from the perspective of the listener, but also from the perspective of the speaker. This point is made by Meier (1992: 31), who focuses on the face repair of the speaker rather than the listener: Apologies, apologies, justifications, etc. are polite acts that occur alongside other face-threatening behaviors. are not considered as events. . They are simply an attempt to undo the damage to the image caused by the nexus of liability between the actor and the wrongdoing. In contrast to Brown and Levinson, corrective work was defined as a face-saving device by S (not H). H's concern for face is a byproduct of S's attempt to save face. Thus, the representation of S will be fundamental. The goal of subsequent correction work is to repair S's image. Meier (2004: 3) presents a model of apology and puts the speaker at its center, which is shown in the following figure:

According to Meier (2004:3), apologies can serve as a tool for image maintenance. Furthermore, he argues that the main motivating force behind apologies is the image of the speaker in the eyes of the listener, who is the judge of the appropriateness or effectiveness of apologetic strategies for a given context. is the situation .

I am sorry to have occasioned pain to anyone. It has been most unconsciously done, however, and I hope will be of short duration. The feelings which you tell me have long prevented the acknowledgment of your regard can have little difficulty in overcoming it after this explanation. "[Jane Austin. Pride and prejudice]

According to Meyer, apologetics are seen as largely audience-supportive, according to Brown and Levinson's "almost exclusive concern with H's face" (1995: 383). However, he observes that Leech (1983) classifies apology as a positive politeness strategy and Holmes (1990) considers the speaker's positive face. Holmes notes that the function of apologies is "an attempt to simultaneously satisfy the positive face needs of the speaker and the face needs of the victim" (1990: 162). The following example provided by Holmes (ibid.) illustrates such a situation:

[A calls B to warn him of possible inconvenience.]

A: I'm sorry but I'm going to be a bit late for work. The buses aren't off strike yet and with it being a wet Friday, it'll probably be a while until my taxi arrives.

B: Uh-huh as long as you're here by six, cos I'm going then.

In this interaction, speaker B is talking about the potential loss of speaker B (sorry), but he is trying to compensate for his loss of positive face by explaining why the offense cannot be avoided. Holmes (ibid.) also refers to cases where the speaker tries to change the positive face of the listener:

A: Oh I am sorry - it's Dr. Jack not Mr. Forgive me.

[B smiles in an embarrassed way and addresses C.]

B: Nice to meet you.

Although we have seen how an apology can change the face of a speaker, it also has the power to make the speaker appear vulnerable. Deborah Tannen (1998) in her article Apology: What It Means to Say 'I'm Sorry' describes the situation in which President Clinton testified in the Lewinsky affair, after which he was criticized by the press for not apologizing sufficiently. criticized by . A more specific apology might explain why he weakened his position. Tannen refers to a hidden form of apology. On the other hand, he notes, "although many people resist apologizing, a willingness to apologize can be a sign of strength because it risks making the apologetic appear weak." 'reveals that it is reliable enough to act' (Tannen 1998).

Ogiermann (2009: 53) concludes that there are offenses that can cause positive and negative face damage. Since the speaker and the listener have both face types, "corrective exchanges can affect four faces." To clarify the implementation

of the four-faced apology, Ogiermann suggests the following table: According to Cohen and Olstein (1983), the expression of an apology is mainly one that conveys the meaning of apology or regret. includes specific affective force indicating devices (IFIDs) that are words or formulaic phrases. These formulaic expressions include performative verbs such as "sorry," "apologize," or "excuse." Because this type of apology involves direct regret and asking for forgiveness, they are considered direct apologies. In the case of English, the data showed that a direct apology was the most common apology strategy. Holmes (1990) describes apologetic strategies used in New Zealand English using ethnographic research, which he used to collect data from naturally occurring conversations and apologetic exchanges with college students. built a corpus based on ethnographic methodology. After completing the study, he found that almost half of the apologies included an expression of apology, specifically an expression of regret for the behavior.

Apologies don't always include active verbs. A variety of verbs or clauses can be used to convey the meaning of a speech act (Searle, 1976). Indirect apologies can be used in a variety of ways. Cohen & Olshtain (1983) classified indirect apologies in the following ways: explanation, acknowledgment of responsibility, offer of correction, promise of patience, and giving an explanation for the action are indirect apology strategies. possible . As for the formula, the perpetrator of the act uses the explanation for the offense. For example, to apologize for being late for class, a student can explain that his car had a flat tire on the way. This apology strategy may or may not be acceptable depending on contextual factors; culture, seriousness of the act, age, gender, specific situation and various other factors. Holmes (1990) noted that explanation of action was the second most preferred apologetic strategy used in New Zealand English and the most frequently used indirect apologetic strategy.

"Admission of responsibility," which involves the speaker's acceptance of blame or responsibility, is another indirect way of apologizing. A speaker can use different sub-groups to convey the meaning of responsibility or even to deny responsibility. Such subsets can be listed as follows:

A. acceptance of blame: e.g. "It's my fault,"

B. expressing a lack of self: e.g. "I was confused,"

C. expressing lack of intent: "I didn't mean to" (Cohen & Olshtain, 1983).

In other cases, speakers may offer to repair the damage caused by his actions. In certain contexts, repair may include repairing or replacing a product that is damaged by the infringer or remedying the inconvenience caused by the act. For

example, in the case of a criminal apologizing for breaking into another's computer, the proposed apology might be "I'll buy you a new one." This type of action may or may not require action based on the listener's response. A forbearance promise is another type of implicit strategy that promises a future action or that the action will not be repeated. This particular type of indirect apology strategy depends on the situation and is not the most common apology strategy.

From the observed analysis, it is clear that the social status plays an important role in the daily conversations of the characters, and in most cases they prefer to use the strategy of apologizing depending on the situation and keep in mind the social status of the interlocutor.

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